

First characterization of the algal species found in the hypersaline lake of Lingua, Salina island, Aeolian archipelago, Sicily, Italy

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Introduction

This report summarizes the sampling activities carried out in September 2025 at the hypersaline pond of Lingua, on Salina Island, Aeolian Islands, Sicily, Italy (Bonasera et al. 2022), with the aim of obtaining a characterization of its microbial community, with particular attention to the algal component. Algae were considered a priority in the analysis because of their ecological role in hypersaline environments as primary producers and as indicators of the site's environmental conditions (Shadrin and Anufrieva 2020; Keneally et al. 2025). The lake area extends for about 15000 m², its maximum depth is about 3 m, and its microbial community was never described before. This lake has distinctive environmental characteristics, related to its high salinity, shallow depth, strong exposure to solar radiation, and seasonal variability in physicochemical parameters.

The investigation falls within a context of naturalistic and scientific interest, since hypersaline environments are distinctive ecosystems characterized by selective physicochemical conditions that favor the development of highly specialized biological communities (McGenity, Terry J. and Aharon Oren 2012; Baxter 2018). Knowledge of the microbial biodiversity of these environments is particularly relevant for ecological purposes (Oren 2024), for the enhancement of the area's natural heritage, and for biotechnological applications (DasSarma et al. 2010).

The main objectives of the sampling campaign were:

- to document the presence of microorganisms in the hypersaline pond of Lingua and provide a preliminary description of the microbial diversity and abundance;
- to characterize the algal component by identifying the main morphotypes;
- to cultivate and isolate the sampled algal species, thereby contributing new strains to the Algal Collection at Federico II University of Naples (ACUF);
- to collect material for subsequent taxonomic, ecological, and molecular investigations;
- to obtain photographic documentation through optical micrographs supporting the observations.

Material and Methods

Sampling activities, physicochemical parameters, and samples preservation

Sampling was carried out between 7 and 10 September 2025 at the pond, selecting twelve sampling points along the shores that were representative of the conditions observed at the time of the survey. A sampling point map (**Figure 1.**) was generated by R program, combining sampling point coordinates with georeferenced sampling site map (QGIS, <https://qgis.org/it/thank-you/>).

Water temperature (temperature probe included in XS pHmeter), conductivity (Hanna HI8733 conductivity meter), pH (handheld XS pHmeter), and GPS coordinates were measured and registered for each sampling point. Several qualitative environmental observations were recorded, including water color, presence of surface mat or visible aggregates, and presence of characteristic colors and odors.

Surface water, suspended material like mat and plants, biofilms, aggregates, and surface sediments were collected in sterile falcon tubes and preserved at ambient temperature for 48 hours. Once samples arrived in the laboratory, several preservation conditions were activated according to the type of experiment and analysis, e. g. culturomic, strain isolation, molecular analysis, chemical analysis, and microscopy.

Planktonic community samples for molecular analysis were collected through filtration on 0.22 μm membrane (Millipore Sterivex) and preserved at 4°C. When possible, more than 400 mL of lake water was filtered.

A 2.5% glutaraldehyde solution in the phosphate buffer was used to chemically fix a portion of the sample, immediately after sampling. These samples were designated for electron microscopy, and were preserved at 4°C until their utilization.

Samples of the filtered lake water on 0.22 μm membrane were collected for the characterization of the major and minor chemical elements.

A portion of the sampled biological materials were inoculated in artificially prepared media while on site. In particular, different enriching media were prepared by supplying different sodium chloride amounts to the artificial sea water (ASW) (<https://utex.org/products/artificial-seawater-medium?variant=30991787884634>), exploring the 0 - 300 g L⁻¹ salt concentrations as selective conditions.

Samples of the surrounding sea water were collected and used as reference and background in each analysis and experiment, both for the abiotic and the biotic aspects, following the same above reported methodology.

Microscopic observation and picture analysis

Microscopic observations of the original samples were done by a Nikon Eclipse 800 microscope, employing objectives from 5x to 100x magnifications, in order to examine both sample diversity and abundance, and morphological details of individual cellular structures. The observations were conducted using DIC (Differential Interference Contrast), which increased the contrast of transparent structures and made it possible to highlight the morphological details of the microorganisms more clearly. A first run of observation was concluded in the first 4 days after sampling. In the meantime, samples were preserved at 22 °C under 12 hours light and 12 hours dark circadian cycle. Further observations were conducted on enriched cultures, following their evolution through time.

Preliminary results

Sampling points and physicochemical environmental parameters

Measurements of physicochemical parameters showed mean values for temperature, pH, and conductivity of 32.8 ± 1.5 °C, 8.4 ± 0.2 , and 92.3 ± 4.4 mS cm⁻¹, respectively. Nevertheless, the different sampling points were characterized by values that were, in some cases, significantly different, resulting in differences in the microbial diversity observed (Table 1.).

Figure 1. (a) Geographic location of the study area in Italy. (b) Georeferenced sampling site map, reporting the sampling points marked with red points and numbered from 1 to 12.

Table 1. Sampling point coordinates and physicochemical parameters.

Sampling point	Latitude	Longitude	pH	Temperature [°C]	Conductivity [mS cm ⁻¹]
1	38.53694	14.87056	8.03	29.8	91.3
2	38.53694	14.87056	8.03	29.8	91.3
3	38.53694	14.87056	8.03	29.8	91.3
4	38.53694	14.86972	8.07	31.8	91.9
5	38.53694	14.86917	8.07	31.8	91.9
6	38.53694	14.86917	8.3	32.9	92.8
7	38.53694	14.86861	8.45	33.3	96.2
8	38.53694	14.86778	8.6	35.5	98.8
9	38.53750	14.86806	8.59	32	92.5
10	38.53833	14.86917	8.24	33.1	92.7
11	38.53806	14.87000	8.58	33.5	82.6
12	38.53722	14.87083	8.5	33	92.1

Micrographic documentation

Microscopic observations revealed the presence of a structured microbial community, comprising microalgae and cyanobacteria, coccoid and bacillary prokaryotes, colonial and single celled organisms, protists, and zooplankton. In particular, the preliminary analysis pointed out that the main algae morphotypes were:

- filamentous and unicellular cyanobacteria, both solitary and colonial, of the *Halotheca*, *Oscillatoria*, *Gomphosphaeria*, *Aphanocapsa*, and *Chroococcus* genera;
- Green microalgae of the *Dunaliella* and *Botryococcus* genera;
- Mainly pennate diatoms;

Moreover, algae pigmentation includes green, dark brown, red-purple, and golden-yellow color gradations, reflecting the main color of each associated sampling point.

Below are reported the light micrographs of the original samples—observation were done within four day after the sampling. Detailed description is reported in each picture caption. Species level characterization of algae strains will be provided in document upgrades, once molecular analysis results will be obtained.

Figure 2. (a) Photograph of sampling point 1 (Figure 1.) ($T = 29.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.0$, $\sigma = 91.3\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the golden-brown biofilm that extends over the lake floor—white scale bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing biofilm structure composed mainly of bacillary-colonial and filamentous cyanobacteria—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(i) are 1000x magnifications, showing how microorganisms are organized inside the biofilms—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d) Colonial bacillary cyanobacterium of the genus *Halothece*; (e) *Halothece* colony and golden-brown filamentous cyanobacteria of *Oscillatoria* genus; (f) *Halothece* colonies embedded in extra polymeric substances (EPS); (g)-(i) show the high density that characterize the interior space of a biofilm, including small prokaryotic cells, cell debris, and EPS. (l) shows a protist.

Figure 3. (a) Photograph of sampling point 2 (Figure 1.) ($T = 29.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.0$, $\sigma = 91.3\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the yellowish-white floating mat upon the lake surface—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, highlighting that the structure is mainly composed of filamentous and bacillary colonial cyanobacteria—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(n) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out that the main included species are colonial and filamentous cyanobacteria—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d) *Halothece*; *Croococcus* (d), (g), (m); *Gomphosphaeria* (e), (h); *Oscillatoria* (e)-(n); Pennate diatoms are embedded inside mat structure as reported in (f).

Figure 4. (a) Photograph of sampling point 3 (Figure 1.) ($T = 29.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.0$, $\sigma = 91.3\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the yellowish-white foam floating upon the lake surface—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that foam's biomass content includes mainly pennate diatoms and round green cells—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(n) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out some details of cells inside the foam—white bars correspond to 10 μm . Pennate diatom details are reported in (e)-(n) and (n). *Chroococcus* and *Gonphosphaeria* are reported in (e) and (d), (m), respectively.

Figure 5. (a) Photograph of sampling point 4 (Figure 1.) ($T = 31.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.1$, $\sigma = 91.9\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the yellowish-brown sediments—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b)-(n) are 1000x magnification, showing details of the microbial community included in sediments—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (b), (d) Gomphosphaeria; (c), (d) filamentous cyanobacteria; (e) small motile green cell resembling *Dunaliella* genus algae; (f)-(h) pennate diatoms, cyanobacteria, and sediments; (i), (l) *Chroococcus* cyanobacteria; (m), (n) pennate diatoms.

Figure 6. (a) Photograph of sampling point 5 (Figure 1.) ($T = 31.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.1$, $\sigma = 91.9\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the yellowish-brown biofilms that extend on lake floor rocks—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that biofilm is mainly composed of filamentous cyanobacteria and pennate diatoms, together with some round green cells—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)–(n) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out detailed morphology of present organisms—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d), (g) Golden *Oscillatoria*; (e), (i), (l), (n) golden *Oscillatoria* and *Chroococcus*; (f), (h) pennate diatoms; (m) golden *Oscillatoria* and *Gomphosphaeria*.

Figure 7. (a) Photograph of sampling point 6 (Figure 1.) ($T = 32.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.3$, $\sigma = 92.8\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the orange-brown biofilms, anchored to lake sediments and partially fluctuating—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnification and point out that pennate diatoms together with filamentous cyanobacteria constitute that orange biofilms—white bars correspond to 20 μm . (d) and (e) are 200x magnifications, providing dimensions and details of the pennate diatoms and dinoflagellates—white bars are 10 μm . (f)–(u) are 400x magnifications, providing details of the present organisms—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (f), (g), (l) pennate diatoms; (h), (m), (n), (t) pennate diatoms, filamentous cyanobacteria, small colonial cells, cell debris, and EPS; (i) pennate diatoms, *Halothece*, *Gonphosphaeria*, small colonial cell, cell debris, and EPS; (o) pennate diatom, *Halothece* embedded in EPS; (p) pennate diatoms, *Oscillatoria*, small colonial cells; (q) pennate diatoms, small colonial cells embedded in EPS; (r) *Oscillatoria*, *Choococcus*, pennate diatoms, *Halothece* embedded in EPS; (s) pennate diatoms embedded in EPS; (u) pennate diatoms and *Chroococcus*.

Figure 8. (a) Photograph of sampling point 7 (Figure 1.) ($T = 33.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.4$, $\sigma = 96.2\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the foggy-floating mat on the lake surface—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b)–(e) are 200x magnification, reporting the mat structured upon pennate diatoms and colonial cyanobacteria—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (f)–(s) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out details of the extra polymeric matrix and cell included inside the mat—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (f) brown colonial cells, *Chroococcus*; (g) pennate diatoms, small colonial cells, and filamentous cyanobacteria embedded in EPS; (h) and (l) colonial green algae embedded in brown EPS; (i) and (s) filamentous organism; (m) filamentous cyanobacteria and small colonial cells embedded in brown EPS; (n) filamentous and small colonial cyanobacteria, pennate diatom details; (o) *Chroococcus*; (p) pennate diatoms, green colonial algae embedded in grey-brown EPS; (q) pennate diatom details, filamentous cyanobacteria, small colonial cells embedded in grey-brown EPS; (r) pennate diatom and small unicellular organisms.

Figure 9. (a) Photograph of sampling point 8 (figure 1.) ($T = 35.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.6$, $\sigma = 98.8\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the floating green-brown microbial mat—white scale bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that the green color is mainly due to a filamentous cyanobacterium—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(n) are 400x magnifications, highlighting that biomass is composed of different filamentous cyanobacteria of the *Oscillatoria* genus, small reddish motile algae of the *Dunaliella* genus, and bigger round two-cell colonial *Chroococcus* genus cyanobacteria—white scale bars correspond to 10 μm . (d) *Oscillatoria* and small penate diatom; (e), (f), (g), (l), (m) *Oscillatoria* cyanobacteria of two different dimensions—bigger *Oscillatoria* do fragmentation with necridia; (h) small motile reddish cell of *Dunaliella* genus; (i) motile cell of the *Dunaliella* genus and *Chroococcus* cyanobacteria; (n) *Oscillatoria* hormogonium and filamentous cyanobacteria. (o)-(qq) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out details of organisms included in the floating mat—white bars correspond to 10 μm .

Figure 10. (a) Photograph of sampling point 9 (Figure 1.) ($T = 32.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.6$, $\sigma = 92.5\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the light-brown floating mat anchored to the plants of the *Arundo L.* genus—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that the mat structure includes filamentous cyanobacteria, pennate diatoms, and round green cells—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(q) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out cell details of the organisms included in the mat—white bars correspond to 10 μm .

Figure 11. (a) Photograph of sampling point 10 (figure 1.) ($T = 33.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.2$, $\sigma = 92.7\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the golden-brown lake floor—white scale bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that the lake floor color is mainly due to pennate diatoms and filamentous cyanobacteria—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(r) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out details of the cellular organisms included in lake sediments—white bars correspond to 10 μm .

Figure 12. (a) Photograph of sampling point 11 (Figure 1.) ($T = 35.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.6$, $\sigma = 82.6\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the dark and light-brown sediments—white bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b) and (c) are 40x magnifications, showing that sediments include pennate diatoms and filamentous organisms—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d)-(z) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out cell details of the organisms included in sediments—white bars correspond to 10 μm . (d) and (g) *Beggiatoa* bacteria.

Figure 13. (a) Photograph of sampling point 12 (figure 1.) ($T = 33.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{pH} = 8.5$, $\sigma = 92.1\text{ mS cm}^{-1}$), showing the opaque mat on the lake surface—white scale bar corresponds to 10 cm. (b)-(h) are 1000x magnifications, pointing out that mat is composed of *Aphanocapsa*, *Halothece*, and *Chroococcus* cyanobacteria genera—white scale bars correspond to 10 μm .

Discussion

This study provides the first description of the microbial community associated with the Salina Lingua hypersaline lake. The results highlight the biological relevance of this pond as an environment capable of supporting a specialized halotolerant microbial community. The lake floor was extensively covered by a golden-brown biofilm, while dense dark green-grey mats were observed floating on the water surface in selected areas. The pigmentation, morphology, and abundant extracellular polymeric material embedding the cells suggest adaptive responses to elevated salinity, high osmotic pressure, and intense solar radiation.

The physicochemical parameters indicate that Salina Lingua lake can be classified as a thalassohaline hypersaline aquatic ecosystem, characterized by a salinity of approximately 6%, NaCl as the dominant salt, and a mean pH of 8.4. Under these conditions, cyanobacteria represented the main biomass component, forming structured mats and biofilms dominated by genera such as *Halothece*, *Oscillatoria*, and *Chroococcus* (Gerasimenko and Burakova 2009). In sampling areas where salinity reached higher values, up to approximately 70 g L⁻¹, green algae belonging to the genus *Dunaliella* became dominant (Oren 2014). Conversely, shallow marginal zones appeared to provide favorable ecological niches for pennate diatoms, which flourished and became important primary producers (Kókai et al. 2015).

Taken together, these observations suggest that Salina Lingua lake represents a valuable natural model system for investigating microbial adaptation to hypersaline conditions. In particular, the spatial heterogeneity observed along the lake margins may provide useful insights into phytoplankton blooms (Muir and Perissinotto 2011), seasonal restructuring of trophic chains (Belovsky et al. 2025), tolerance to low water activity (Brown 1976; Grant 2004; Stevenson et al. 2015), and microbial strategies associated with transitions between aquatic and terrestrial habitats.

Conclusions

The sampling campaign carried out at the hypersaline pond of Lingua on Salina made it possible to document the presence of a diversified microbial community, in which the algal component appears to be of particular interest. Preliminary microscopic observations indicate that the site represents a suitable habitat for the development of microorganisms adapted to extreme saline conditions, confirming the naturalistic and scientific value of the area. The documentation collected provides a useful basis for future investigations aimed at improving knowledge about hypersaline systems.

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Bibliography

Baxter, Bonnie. 2018. ‘Great Salt Lake Microbiology: A Historical Perspective’. *International Microbiology* 21 (September). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10123-018-0008-z>.

Belovsky, Gary E., Chad Larson, Younjin Han, Richard Wilson, Hannah J. Appiah-Madson, and Heidi Mahon. 2025. ‘Environment and Phytoplankton Relative Abundances in a Hypersaline Lake: 27 Years in Great Salt Lake, USA and Experiments’. *Aquatic Ecology* 59 (2): 707–24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10452-025-10190-1>.

- Bonasera, Mauro, Ciro Cerrone, Fabiola Caso, Stefania Lanza, Giandomenico Fubelli, and Giovanni Randazzo. 2022. 'Geomorphological and Structural Assessment of the Coastal Area of Capo Faro Promontory, NE Salina (Aeolian Islands, Italy)'. *Land* 11 (7): 1106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11071106>.
- Brown, A. D. 1976. 'Microbial Water Stress.' *Bacteriological Reviews* 40 (4): 803–46. <https://doi.org/10.1128/br.40.4.803-846.1976>.
- DasSarma, Priya, James A. Coker, Valerie Huse, and Shiladitya DasSarma. 2010. 'Halophiles, Industrial Applications'. In *Encyclopedia of Industrial Biotechnology*, 1st edn, by Michael C. Flickinger. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470054581.eib439>.
- Gerasimenko, L., and Olga Burakova. 2009. 'Halophilic Algal-Bacterial and Cyanobacterial Communities and Their Role in Carbonate Precipitation'. *Paleontological Journal* 43 (December): 940–57. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031030109080127>.
- Grant, W. D. 2004. 'Life at Low Water Activity.' *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 359 (1448): 1249–67. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2004.1502>.
- Keneally, Christopher, Virginie Gaget, Daniel Chilton, et al. 2025. 'Microbial Ecology in Hypersaline Coastal Lagoons: A Model for Climate-Induced Coastal Salinisation and Eutrophication'. *Earth-Science Reviews* 266 (July): 105150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2025.105150>.
- Kókai, Zsuzsanna, István Bácsi, Péter Török, et al. 2015. 'Halophilic Diatom Taxa Are Sensitive Indicators of Even Short Term Changes in Lowland Lotic Systems'. *Acta Botanica Croatica* 74 (October): 287–302. <https://doi.org/10.1515/botcro-2015-0025>.
- McGenity, Terry J. and Aharon Oren. 2012. *Life at Extremes: Environments, Organisms and Strategies for Survival*. 20 Hypersaline Environments. CAB International 2012. E.M. Bell.
- Muir, David G., and Renzo Perissinotto. 2011. 'Persistent Phytoplankton Bloom in Lake St. Lucia (iSimangaliso Wetland Park, South Africa) Caused by a Cyanobacterium Closely Associated with the Genus *Cyanothece* (Synechococcaceae, Chroococcales)'. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 77 (17): 5888–96. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00460-11>.
- Oren, Aharon. 2014. 'The Ecology of *Dunaliella* in High-Salt Environments'. *Journal of Biological Research-Thessaloniki* 21 (1): 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40709-014-0023-y>.
- Oren, Aharon. 2024. 'Novel Insights into the Diversity of Halophilic Microorganisms and Their Functioning in Hypersaline Ecosystems'. *Npj Biodiversity* 3 (1): 18. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44185-024-00050-w>.
- Shadrin, Nickolai, and Elena Anufriieva. 2020. 'Structure and Trophic Relations in Hypersaline Environments'. *Biology Bulletin Reviews*, March 10, 418–27. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079086420010065>.
- Stevenson, Andrew, Jonathan A. Cray, Jim P. Williams, et al. 2015. 'Is There a Common Water-Activity Limit for the Three Domains of Life?' *The ISME Journal* 9 (6): 1333–51. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2014.219>.